

Name of the study:

An Ecopath model to estimate trophic positions for ecological groups in the Barents Sea

Author(s): Torstein Pedersen

Date: 2022

DOI (if applicable): [Click or tap here to enter DOI.](#)

Repository (e.g. GitHub): [Click or tap here to enter repository.](#)

Prior model developments and historical context:

The Ecopath model for the Barents Sea Large Marine Ecosystem for year 2000 comprise 108 functional groups including primary producers, pelagic and benthic invertebrates and fish, birds, seals, whales, and polar bear (Pedersen et al. 2021). The model is a mass-balance model with high trophic resolution and is less fish-centered than most other Ecopath models. The model was parametrized based on information for functional groups on biomass, production, and consumption per biomass ratios, catch and diet composition from large numbers of sources. A dynamic version of the model has been calibrated to time-series for biomass, catches and other variables for the time-period 1950-2013 (Pedersen et al. 2021). In this application, trophic position estimates from the year 2000 Ecopath model were compared to independent estimates of earlier published trophic levels for functional groups from stable isotopes.

1. Objectives

1.1. Context and motivations

1. What are the objectives of the model application

The objective of this application of Ecopath is to estimate trophic positions (TPs) for functional groups in the Barents Sea for year 2000.

2. Why is the model suitable to address the objectives?

Ecopath models are suitable to estimate trophic positions as they can efficiently integrate and use the empirical data (i.e., diet composition, biomasses, gross efficiencies, assimilation efficiencies of functional groups needed to estimate trophic positions).

3. What would count as successful in achieving these objectives?

It would be regarded as successful if the estimates of trophic positions derived from the Ecopath model are consistent with independent data.

1.2. Specific model setup

4. Are there any deviations from the original model description?

- a. In the model assumptions?
- b. In the model structure – submodels, variables, components, scales?
- c. In the model details – parameter values, functional relationships
- d. In the model forcing – initial conditions, boundary conditions, observation forcing, maps?

There are no deviation from the original model (Pedersen et al. 2021).

2. Patterns

2.1. Selected patterns

5. Which ecological patterns are used for the model evaluation?

Trophic Position (TP) is the essential ecological pattern.

6. Why are these patterns important/essential to address the objectives?

The objective of the model application is to assess TPs. This pattern is directly related to the objective and a good test of the model's ability and quality.

2.2. Independent data

7. Where do the independent data originate from?

The independent data consists of TL estimates and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values derived from stable isotope measurements. The stable isotope data were collected from the literature on a large number of species and from 83 functional groups from ca. 92 publications from studies within the Barents Sea LME (Pedersen in prep.). These data originate from studies that have sampled organisms and detritus in the field and analyzed the stable isotope composition ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$). The stable isotope data from various species were allocated to functional groups identical to those in the Ecopath model. The temporal and spatial extent varies for each stable isotope data set. There were estimates of standard deviation for most $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values.

8. What are the extent and resolution of the independent data?

The data comes from studies carried out all over the Barents Sea LME area. Much of the data comes from studies from fjord areas and the possible effect of habitat (fjord vs. open water) on the TP vs. $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values have been analyzed showing that data from fjords are similar to open water except for some benthic invertebrate groups in some fjords (Pedersen, in prep.). The data set contains about 1800 $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values based on about 8000 individuals or pooled replicates from several small individuals. The data were mostly sampled after 1990.

9. How representative are the independent data of the ecological processes?

Overall, the representativeness of the data was good although it varied between groups due to varying number of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -values for each ecological group and variable spatial representativeness. This comparison of trophic positions estimates has much more groups ($n = 83$) and are based on a larger number of primary data entries than earlier published comparisons in marine ecosystems. It also had a higher trophic resolution than most other similar studies and relatively. A total of 77% of the groups in the Ecopath model had TP estimates from stable isotope data.

10. Are there estimates of independent data accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

The majority of ecological groups had more than one $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value and standard deviation and standard error of the mean $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ value for the group was calculated (Pedersen, in prep.).

11. How are the independent data processed to represent the selected pattern and are assumptions made to derive these patterns from the data?

For TP values reported in literature, no assumptions were needed (the authors of the publications have assumed trophic enrichment factors (TEF)). In addition, for all $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values, TPs based on the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values were calculated using a trophic enrichment factor estimated (linear $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ stable isotope TL relationship) (Post 2002). An alternative nonlinear relationship between $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and TP (scaled trophic enrichment factor) was also evaluated (Hussey et al. 2014). Average values of $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ for each functional group were calculated and TP were calculated using the respective TEF's. Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?

2.3. Model outputs

12. Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?

The model output used were the proportions of prey in the diets of the predators.

13. Have the outputs been post-processed, and how?

Diet proportions were processed to calculate TPs in the following way: $TP_j = 1 + \sum DC_{ij} TP_i$ where j is the predator, i is the prey and DC_{ij} is the proportion of prey in the diet of predator j . Detritus groups are assumed to have TP of 1.0. This post-processing is done within the Ecopath with Ecosim program.

14. Are there estimates of model output accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

Since uncertainty in diet composition was not included in the Monte Carlo simulation producing confidence limits of model output values, the confidence limits were not used in the TP comparison.

15. Are additional assumptions made when deriving patterns from model outputs?

It was assumed that the year 2000 Ecopath model structure and trophic positions were similar to the average for the period 1960-2015 for which independent stable isotope data exist.

3. Evaluation

3.1. Evaluation methodology

16. Are sanity checks conducted? If so, what is the method used?

- a. Which data and patterns are used for this?
- b. Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?

Data and patterns are used for this: a sanity check according to recommendations by Link (2010) was performed. The data used for this were Ecopath input values for functional groups on biomass, production per biomass and consumption per biomass. Biomass, production per biomass and consumption per biomass of various functional groups are plotted versus trophic level of the functional groups to judge if patterns are realistic compared to expected relationship between the variables. Since Ecopath can estimate P/Bs and biomasses of some functional groups, some output values are also included in this check. It is also checked that ecotrophic efficiencies are equal to or less than 1.0 meaning that the production values of functional groups are sufficient to supply fishery catches and predatory consumption.

This was the only pattern evaluated.

17. What is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from independent data with patterns from the model?

- a. What is the rationale for choosing this method?
- b. How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?
- c. Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?

The evaluation was performed by plotting the TPs from Ecopath and literature against each other and testing if they are correlated. Whether TPs from Ecopath and published TPs from the Barents Sea for the functional groups were equal on average was examined using a sign test on pairs of TP values from Ecopath and stable isotopes (one pair for each ecological group). In addition, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values and TP derived from $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values assuming a common trophical enrichment factor were plotted versus TPs from the Ecopath model TPs and correlation coefficient (Pearson) and R^2 were calculated.

Rationale for choosing this method: This is a simple and transparent method for comparing two variables.

Handling of observational and/or model output uncertainty: Ecopath model output uncertainty was not included and only point estimates from Ecopath and stable isotopes were used in the analysis. Uncertainty in the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values are considered in the model evaluation.

Model evaluation reporting form, OPE (Objective Patterns Evaluation)

Specific assumptions: The method (correlation) assumes normally distributed TPs from Ecopath and from $\delta^{15}\text{N}$.

18. Is there a threshold level (match between observed and modelled patterns) that can separate acceptable from unacceptable models?

A threshold level for R^2 equal to 0.5 for the model TPs vs $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values was used to separate acceptable from unacceptable Ecopath models. The threshold is based on the level of R^2 from other similar studies (Kline et al. 1998, Nilsen et al. 2008, Navarro et al. 2011, Milessi et al. 2020).

19. How comparable are the patterns derived from the model and those derived from the independent data?

The TPs derived from $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ -values and from the Ecopath model outputs are comparable given a number of assumptions (e.g. q15) and assuming that the output of the data processing outlined in q11 and q13 produce ecologically comparable patterns.

3.2. Sensitivities

20. Has a model sensitivity analysis been performed, and how?

- a. on the model structure?
- b. on the model

on the model structure?

No

on the model parametrization?

Yes, a Monte Carlo simulation procedure was applied to estimate uncertainty in model output values based on uncertainty in model parameters. It did not include uncertainty in diet matrix due to computational limitations. In the Monte Carlo simulation, random values of model input values were drawn from user-defined uniform distributions with width corresponding to $2 \cdot \text{CV}$ for the input values. CV for input value is equal to the standard error/mean and were based on estimates of standard errors or on user-assessed uncertainty levels when standard errors have not been estimated. Only balanced models were accepted as valid Monte Carlo replicates.

21. Which elements are the modelled patterns most sensitive to?

- a. input parameters
- b. priors and assumptions
- c. structural elements

Given the method for calculating TPs in Ecopath, these are assumed to be most sensitive to the input specification of the diet composition for the ecological groups.

22. How sensitive are the modelled patterns to the choice of initial conditions, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution?

The Ecopath model is not dynamic or spatial and has no spin up time or spatial resolution. It represents the average conditions of a year. Thus, this is not relevant for this application. Generally, the level of uncertainty in the output values from the Ecopath model is similar to the level of uncertainty in the input values (Essington 2007).

23. How sensitive is the model evaluation to the independent data availability and uncertainty?

We have not tested how sensitive the model evaluation is to data availability and uncertainty. The large number ($n = 83$) of functional groups that had TP values from both the Ecopath model and stable isotopes made the evaluation less sensitive to uncertainty in single functional group TP values.

24. How much is the model evaluation constrained by computational or theoretical limits?

The model evaluation is to a small degree constrained by computational and theoretical limits. Uncertainty in diet data could not be evaluated by Monte Carlo simulation because of computational limits.

25. How does the perceived performance of the model depend on the chosen evaluation methodology?

The perceived performance of the model depends on the chosen evaluation methodology to a small degree. The chosen methodology depends on very few assumptions and is transparent and based on a very large data material both for the Ecopath model and the independent stable isotope data. This reduces the probability that a single or few critical assumptions or uncertain data points have a major influence on the results of the evaluation.

References

- Essington, T.E. (2007). Evaluating the sensitivity of a trophic mass-balance model (Ecopath) to imprecise data inputs. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 64(4), 628-637.
- Hussey, N.E., MacNeil, M.A., McMeans, B.C., Olin, J.A., Dudley, S.F., Cliff, G., et al. (2014). Rescaling the trophic structure of marine food webs. *Ecology letters* 17(2), 239-250.
- Kline, T.C., Pauly, D., and Quinn, T.J.I.I. (1998). "Cross-validation for trophic level estimates from a mass-balance model of Prince William Sound using N15/N14 data," in *Fishery Stock Assessment Models*. (Fairbanks: Alaska Sea Grant College Program Report No. AK-SG-98-01, University of Alaska Fairbanks), 693-702.
- Link, J.S. (2010). Adding rigor to ecological network models by evaluating a set of pre-balance diagnostics: A plea for PREBAL. *Ecological Modelling* 221(12), 1580-1591. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2010.03.012.
- Milessi, A.C., Danilo, C., Laura, R.G., Daniel, C., Javier, S., and Rodriguez-Gallego, L. (2010). Trophic mass-balance model of a subtropical coastal lagoon, including a comparison with a stable isotope analysis of the food-web. *Ecological Modelling* 221(24), 2859-2869. doi: 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2010.08.037.
- Navarro, J., Coll, M., Louzao, M., Palomera, I., Delgado, A., and Forero, M.G. (2011). Comparison of ecosystem modelling and isotopic approach as ecological tools to investigate food webs in the NW Mediterranean Sea. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 401(1-2), 97-104.
- Nilsen, M., Pedersen, T., Nilssen, E.M., and Fredriksen, S. (2008). Trophic studies in a high latitude fjord ecosystem - a comparison of stable isotope analyses ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) and trophic-level estimates from a mass-balance model. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 65, 2791-2806.
- Pedersen (in rev.) Comparison between trophic positions in the Barents Sea from stable isotopes and mass-balance model
- Pedersen, T., Mikkelsen, N., Lindstrøm, U., Renaud, P.E., Nascimento, M.C., Blanchet, M.-A., et al. (2021). Overexploitation, recovery and warming of the Barents Sea ecosystem during 1950-2013. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8, 732637. doi: 732610.733389/fmars.732021.732637.
- Post, D.M. (2002). Using stable isotopes to estimate trophic position: models, methods, and assumptions. *Ecology* 83(3), 703-718.

Name of the study:

Predator-prey interactions cause apparent competition between marine zooplankton groups

Author(s): LC Stige, KØKvile, B Bogstad, Ø Langangen

Date: 2017

DOI (if applicable): <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.2126>

Repository (e.g. GitHub): [Click or tap here to enter repository.](#)

Prior model developments and historical context:

Stige et al. (2018) developed a Gompertz model of intermediate complexity implemented in a Bayesian state-space approach with the purpose of assessing the role of zooplankton on population dynamics of capelin while accounting for feedback-effects of capelin on zooplankton. Those effects are described by a process model which is linked to data by an observation model. This work was motivated by several previous studies on the system. Findings from those studies suggest, on the one side, a positive relationship between zooplankton biomass and growth of individual capelin (Gjørseter 2002) and, on the other side, a negative relationship between the biomass of capelin in the central and northern Barents Sea and the local biomass of krill and copepods (Stige et al. 2014).

1. Objectives

1.1. Context and motivations

1. What are the objectives of the model application

*The objective of the model application is to quantify the association between the dynamics of capelin (*Mallotus villosus*) and its main two prey (krill and *Calanus* species) in the Barents Sea. The model is described in Stige et al. (2018).*

2. Why is the model suitable to address the objectives?

The model used is a state-space model (that is the combination of a process model with underlying variables representing the system state and an observation model) fitted to observation time-series for the three species/groups biomass, in a Bayesian framework. With this model, bottom-up and top-down interaction parameters (i.e., association between zooplankton biomass and capelin individual growth and survival, and correlation between zooplankton biomass and capelin biomass respectively), can be simultaneously estimated, making the model suitable to address the relative importance of bottom-up and top-down processes. The model is fitted to data covering the Barents Sea in the period 1980-2015. In the model, the survival and growth of each capelin age class can be affected by external drivers such as predator and prey abundance as well as fishing and temperature. Outputs of the model include the quantified effects of copepod and krill biomass on capelin age specific length and abundance, and the effects of capelin biomass on copepod and krill biomass.

3. What would count as successful in achieving these objectives?

As a Bayesian Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approach is used to jointly estimate all parameters, the model needs to converge with three parallel MCMC chains well mixed, low autocorrelation after thinning and no trends after the burn-in iterations. Subsequently, the model needs to pass a series of sanity checks to detect anomalous dynamics. In addition, low sensitivity to slight change of model structure and parameters that are fixed during model fitting is important to confirm that the main findings are robust to the key assumptions of the model

1.2. Specific model setup

4. Are there any deviations from the original model description?
 - a. In the model assumptions?
 - b. In the model structure – submodels, variables, components, scales?
 - c. In the model details – parameter values, functional relationships
 - d. In the model forcing – initial conditions, boundary conditions, observation forcing, maps?

This is the original application of the model, as described in Stige et al. (2018)

2. Patterns

2.1. Selected patterns

5. Which ecological patterns are used for the model evaluation?
 - Population trajectories: Inter-annual variation in the biomass of the zooplankton, total biomass of capelin and in age specific abundance and size of capelin.
 - Correlations between prey, i.e., copepod and krill, biomass and capelin biomass, prey biomass and capelin individual growth as well as time-lagged correlations between copepods and krill biomass.
6. Why are these patterns important/essential to address the objectives?

Inter-annual variations in biomass, abundance and size reflect population dynamics and are the central focus of the study, i.e., the objective is to quantify the association between these dynamics. These patterns are derived from observations and are also outputs of the model. They are used to evaluate the fit of the model to observations

Positive correlation of zooplankton biomass with individual growth of capelin suggests bottom-up effects by zooplankton on capelin. Negative correlation between capelin biomass and zooplankton suggests top-down effects.

Time-lagged correlations between copepods and krill to test if simpler analysis methods support apparent competition between krill and copepods, which was one of the inferences from the model.

2.2. Independent data

7. Where do the independent data originate from?

The biological data originated from different scientific surveys, including 0-group trawl surveys performed in fall by Institute of Marine Research (IMR) and Polar Research Institute

Model evaluation reporting form, OPE (Objective Patterns Evaluation)

of Marine Fisheries and Oceanography (PINRO, Eriksen and Prozorkevich 2011), as well as acoustic estimates of abundance at age for the capelin (Eriksen et al. 2017). In addition, reported catches of capelin, absolute abundance of capelin and biomass series of capelin predators (i.e., cod age 3-6 and herring age 1-2) were obtained from ICES 2016 report.

Environmental data (i.e., temperature) correspond to open data provided by National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). All available data was used for model fitting (estimating the model parameters). There is no additional independent data used in the model evaluation.

8. What are the extent and resolution of the independent data?

The observations cover the period 1980-2015. The frequency of sampling was annual and the geographic extension corresponded to the Barents Sea. The Barents Sea region has been subdivided into three regions based on mean sea temperature (Southwestern, central and northern) for the copepod model (details are provided in Table 1)

Table 1: List of observations used for model fitting and evaluation.

Description	Period covered	Frequency	Geographic extension	survey/source	Availability
Capelin abundance (Age 0)	1980-2015	Annual (Aug-Sep)		0-group trawl survey IMR/PINRO	ICES (2016)
Capelin length (Age 0)	1980-2015	Annual (Aug-Sep)		0-group trawl survey IMR/PINRO	annual IMR-PINRO report
Capelin abundance (Age 1-4)	1980-2015	Annual (Sep-Oct)		Acoustic survey IMR/PINRO	ICES (2016)
Capelin length (Age 1-4)	1980-2015	Annual (Sep-Oct)		Acoustic survey IMR/PINRO	annual IMR-PINRO report
Capelin catches	1980-2015	Annual			ICES (2016)
Copepod biomass area density (5261 samples)	1981+1984-2015	Annual Aug-Sep	All Barents Sea, data for three sub regions.	correspond to mesozooplankton (WP2 net sampling with 180 µm mesh size). Biomass ts constructed as in Dalpadado et al. (2012).	IMR (Stige et al. 2014)
Krill biomass area density	1980-2015	Annual Aug-Oct	Entire Barents Sea	Arithmetic mean of day and night catches from pelagic trawls (Eriksen et al. 2016).	
Capelin predators' biomass	1980-2015	Annual		Cod age 3-6 and herring age 1-2	ICES (2016)
Sea Surface Temperature	1980-2015	Monthly (Average May-Oct)	68-80°N And 20-50°E		NOAA_ERSST_V3 data set

9. How representative are the independent data of the ecological processes?

Capelin individual growth and survival is expected to be influenced by the environment and the availability in prey as well as by predators. Zooplankton data from autumn was used as proxy for prey conditions for capelin the subsequent year. As capelin abundance and length at age were collected in autumn each year, those data allow to obtain the length at the end of the growing season. The geographic and depth distribution of the copepod data covered the feeding grounds of capelin well, whereas krill data were only available from upper 60 m of the water column. As the krill conduct diel vertical migration and data were from both day and night catches, it may be assumed that krill abundance in the upper water layers scales with krill abundance in the entire water column

10. Are there estimates of independent data accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

Uncertainties about biological processes and observation noise were explicitly accounted for by an observation model describing the relationship between the modelled (unobserved) processes and the observed variables. As recommended by Ives et al. (2003), best available estimates of observation errors were used, when possible, rather than trying to estimate these from the data. That is, the variances of the observation errors were mostly assumed known when the model was fitted and only the variances of the process errors were estimated. Estimates or "best guesses" of observation errors were available for copepod data, krill data, age-0 capelin length and age-0 to age-4 capelin abundance. Observation error variance for age-1 to age-4 capelin length was estimated from the data. A description of the error associated to each observation is provided in Stige et al. ((2018) Supplementary information). The sensitivity analyses included increasing the assumed observation errors by 50 %

11. How are the independent data processed to represent the selected pattern and are assumptions made to derive these patterns from the data?

Population trajectories: Time series of capelin abundance-at-age, capelin length-at-age and zooplankton biomass from both the data and the model outputs are directly compared and require no additional processing. The abundance and length-at-age were combined with a length-weight relationship to calculate the total stock biomass (TSB), which was compared with data on the TSB.

Correlation: there is no data to compare them. Time-lagged correlations were assessed using least-squares autoregressive models of copepod and krill observation time-series.

2.3. Model outputs

12. Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?

Inter-annual variation in the biomass of the zooplankton, and age specific abundance and size of capelin.

13. Have the outputs been post-processed, and how?

Capelin biomass was calculated from the modelled abundance-at-age and length-at-age based on length-weight relationships described in the literature (Gjørøster 1998).

14. Are there estimates of model output accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

The posterior distributions of the parameters are summarized by the marginal posterior mean and 95% credible interval.

15. Are additional assumptions made when deriving patterns from model outputs?

The length-weight relationship used is based on observations made from 1968 to 1970 only. It is assumed that this relationship has remained unchanged during all the period covered by the model.

3. Evaluation

3.1. Evaluation methodology

16. Are sanity checks conducted? If so, what is the method used?

- a. Which data and patterns are used for this?
- b. Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?

Model convergence was confirmed by a visual inspection of the chains, with all three parallel MCMC chains were well mixed, by the low autocorrelation after thinning and by the absence of trends after the burn-in iterations. In addition, the Gelman and Rubin scale reduction factor, which compares within-chain and between-chain variance, has been used.

Because the Gompertz model assumes a linear relationship on the log-scale between mean year-class length in successive years, relationship between length at age and length at age the next year (figure 7 in Stige et al. 2018) was used to test if this type of model was suitable. In addition, the signs and magnitudes of the associations estimated from the model were checked to be biologically interpretable (e.g. no negative bottom-up effects nor positive top-down).

17. What is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from independent data with patterns from the model?

- a. What is the rationale for choosing this method?
- b. How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?
- c. Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?

The evaluation consisted in a visual check to confirm there were no systematic deviations between fitted means and observed values which would indicate model misspecification.

18. Is there a threshold level (match between observed and modelled patterns) that can separate acceptable from unacceptable models?

No threshold level was defined. Model convergence was the only criteria used.

19. How comparable are the patterns derived from the model and those derived from the independent data?

There is no independent data and the time series of capelin abundance-at-age, capelin length-at-age and zooplankton biomass from both the data and the model outputs are directly compared and require no additional processing. Time-lagged correlations derived from least-squares regression analyses of copepod and krill time-series are comparable to the indirect (capelin-mediated) time-lagged associations between copepods and krill predicted by the state-space model. However, they are sensitive to possible confounding caused by correlations with factors that were not explicitly modelled.

3.2. Sensitivities

20. Has a model sensitivity analysis been performed, and how?

- a. on the model structure?
- b. on the model

Model sensitivity has been performed on the structure of the model. For this purpose, the model was fitted using alternative model formulations which include, for example: an increase of the observation error, density dependence late in life, density dependence in cod predation, temperature effects on zooplankton and capelin abundance after age-0, exploitative competition between the zooplankton groups and the spatial aggregation of the copepods.

Deviation in parameter estimates from the 8 model formulations to the baseline/original model were subsequently compared.

21. Which elements are the modelled patterns most sensitive to?

- a. input parameters
- b. priors and assumptions
- c. structural elements

Model results appeared generally to be robust to key assumptions in the model. Specifically, most parameter estimates were quite similar for the different model formulations considered. Some deviations were observed when measurement errors were assumed to be 50 % higher than in the baseline model (capelin-krill interactions were estimated to be slightly stronger and to have narrower credibility intervals). In models that included terms for density dependence in capelin survival, estimates of copepod effects on capelin survival to ages 1–4 tended to be more negative, but their 95% credibility intervals overlapped with zero for all model formulations considered.

22. How sensitive are the modelled patterns to the choice of initial conditions, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution?

Analysis with a spatially aggregated copepod index led to similar conclusions about bottom-up and top-down effects as the baseline analysis with spatially resolved copepod indices. The estimated bottom-up effects of copepods on capelin abundance at age 1 and on capelin lengths at ages 0 and 2 were in fact slightly more strongly positive when area-aggregated copepod data were used, suggesting that the assumed feeding areas of capelin may have been too small. The robustness of the findings to the use of spatially resolved or spatially aggregated copepod indices make it less likely that results would be qualitatively different if spatially resolved krill indices had been analysed.

23. How sensitive is the model evaluation to the independent data availability and uncertainty?

Some deviations were observed when measurement errors were assumed to be 50 % higher than in the baseline model (capelin-krill interactions were estimated to be slightly stronger and to have narrower credibility intervals).

24. How much is the model evaluation constrained by computational or theoretical limits?

Computational time ranged from hours to days and could therefore limit the number of alternative models tested.

25. How does the perceived performance of the model depend on the chosen evaluation methodology?

No formal model selection has been carried out, consequently it is possible that another model (e.g., one of the alternative models built for sensitivity analysis) could have been selected instead.

References

- Dalpadado, P., Ingvaldsen, R.B., Stige, L.C., Bogstad, B., Knutsen, T., Ottersen, G., and Ellertsen, B. 2012. Climate effects on Barents Sea ecosystem dynamics. *ICES Journal of Marine Science: Journal du Conseil* 69(7): 1303–1316. doi:10.1093/icesjms/fss063.
- Eriksen, E., and Prozorkevich, D. 2011. Chapter 10.2: 0-group survey. In *The Barents Sea - ecosystem, resources and management. Half a century of Russian-Norwegian cooperation*. Edited by T. Jakobsen and V.K. Ozhigin. pp. 557–569.
- Eriksen, E., Skjoldal, H.R., Dolgov, A.V., Dalpadado, P., Orlova, E.L., and Prozorkevich, D.V. 2016. The Barents Sea euphausiids: methodological aspects of monitoring and estimation of abundance and biomass. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 73(6): 1533–1544. doi:10.1093/icesjms/fsw022.
- Eriksen, E., Rune Skjoldal, H., Gjørseter, H., and Primicerio, R. 2017. Spatial and temporal changes in the Barents Sea pelagic compartment during the recent warming. *Progress in Oceanography* 151: 206–226. doi:10.1016/j.pocean.2016.12.009.
- Gjørseter, H. 1998. The population biology and exploitation of capelin (*Mallotus villosus*) in the Barents Sea. *Sarsia* 83(6): 453–496. doi:10.1080/00364827.1998.10420445.
- Gjørseter, H. 2002. Growth of Barents Sea capelin (*Mallotus villosus*) in relation to zooplankton abundance. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 59(5): 959–967. doi:10.1006/jmsc.2002.1240.
- ICES. 2016. Report of the arctic fisheries working group (AFWG). ICES CM 2016/ACOM:06: 631pp.
- Ives, A.R., Dennis, B., Cottingham, K.L., and Carpenter, S.R. 2003. Estimating community stability and ecological interactions from time-series data. *Ecological Monographs* 73(2): 301–330. doi:10.1890/0012-9615(2003)073[0301:ecsaie]2.0.co;2.
- Stige, L.C., Dalpadado, P., Orlova, E., Boulay, A.-C., Durant, J.M., Ottersen, G., and Stenseth, N.Chr. 2014. Spatiotemporal statistical analyses reveal predator-driven zooplankton fluctuations in the Barents Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 120: 243–253. doi:10.1016/j.pocean.2013.09.006.
- Stige, L.C., Kvile, K.Ø., Bogstad, B., and Langangen, Ø. 2018. Predator-prey interactions cause apparent competition between marine zooplankton groups. *Ecology* 99(3): 632–641. doi:10.1002/ecy.2126.

Name of the study:

Non-Deterministic Network Dynamics (NDND) model simulations to assess the persistence of trophic controls in the Barents Sea.

Author(s): Elliot Sivel

Date: 2022

DOI (if applicable): 10.1371/journal.pone.0254015

Repository (e.g. GitHub): [Click or tap here to enter repository.](#)

Prior model developments and historical context:

The NDND model is stochastic mass-balanced food-web model. It was developed to simulate possible food-web dynamics accounting for stochastic variability of natural systems. The first application, for the Benguela upwelling ecosystem was presented by (Mullon et al., 2009). It was later on replicated independently by Planque et al. (2014) for the same ecosystem. Lindstrøm et al. (2017) developed a version of the model for the Barents Sea food-web and applied it to explore the patterns of variability of this ecosystem. The motivation for the current study originated from earlier studies on trophic control in the Barents Sea food-web. The existence and persistence of top-down or bottom-up trophic controls has been debated and remains unclear. Based on empirical observations over the time-period 1970-2009, Johannesen et al. (2012) suggested that trophic controls fluctuated at interdecadal timescales. One aim of the study by Sivel et al. (2021), was to evaluate if decadal fluctuations in trophic controls could emerge from random fluctuations in a constrained food-web. It is the application of the NDND model to the Barents Sea, with this objective, that is evaluated here.

1. Objectives

1.1. Context and motivations

1. What are the objectives of the model application

The aim of the application is to simulate a large set of plausible dynamics of the Barents Sea food-web, and from these simulations, to determine if the patterns of trophic controls (top-down and bottom-up) should be expected to be persistent over multidecadal time-scales.

2. Why is the model suitable to address the objectives?

The NDND is a food-web dynamics model, in which trophic interactions and the fluctuations in the biomass of trophospecies are explicitly represented. The model outputs are therefore suitable to derive estimates of trophic controls. The model is designed to explore the "state-space" of the food-web (Lindstrøm et al., 2017) by simulating constrained stochastic biomass trajectories of all food-web trophospecies. Thus, it is possible to explore whether trophic controls are expected to be persistent across a wide range of possible food-web configurations for the Barents Sea.

3. What would count as successful in achieving these objectives?

The model application would count as successful if all three following conditions are fulfilled:

1) The simulation succeeds. Given the set of model assumptions, input parameters, constraints and initial conditions, a set of possible food-web dynamics that can be computed exists.

2) Simulations are realistic. The biomass of all trophospecies remains within plausible ranges, and when they reach extreme (high or low) values, they tend to return to less extreme values within the time frame of a few years/decades.

3) The simulated food-web configurations should include past observed food-web configurations.

1.2. Specific model setup

4. Are there any deviations from the original model description?
 - a. In the model assumptions?
 - b. In the model structure – submodels, variables, components, scales?
 - c. In the model details – parameter values, functional relationships
 - d. In the model forcing – initial conditions, boundary conditions, observation forcing, maps?

Model assumptions: we use the assumptions from the original NDND model for the Barents Sea (Lindstrøm et al., 2017).

In the model structure: For this application, we added a fisheries module to the original NDND model. This module reproduces the harvest control rules (HCR's) defined for exploited species in the Barents Sea. We applied fisheries for the demersal and pelagic fish groups. We estimated the total catch in both groups using the Baranov equation (Baranov, 1918; Branch, 2009). We made three assumptions for the application of the fisheries module:

- 1) We assume that the ratio catch/stock in numbers is a good proxy for the ratio catch/stock in biomass,*
- 2) We estimate the fishing mortality based on the total stock biomass instead of the spawning stock biomass,*
- 3) We use cod and capelin HCRs to represent the HCRs for demersal and pelagic fish groups, respectively, since cod and capelin are the dominant species within these trophospecies.*

The implementation of this fisheries module requires four new parameters to reconstruct the HCRs and derive the catches: fishing mortality rate (F_{mp} , year^{-1}), target biomass (B_{mp} , tonnes.km^{-2}), trigger biomass (B_{lim} , tonnes.km^{-2}), and natural mortality (M , year^{-1}). Fisheries catches are expressed in tonnes.km^{-2} .

Model details: Refuge biomass values were revised for pelagic and demersal fish.

Model forcing: We did not change the model forcing.

2. Patterns

2.1. Selected patterns

5. Which ecological patterns are used for the model evaluation?

Temporal patterns: we used the variability in trophic control (i.e. top-down or bottom-up) as an ecological pattern for the model evaluation

Spatial patterns: the NDND model, and the objective of this application, does not consider spatial aspects.

Structural, functional patterns: for the evaluations, we used measures of temporal correlation between the simulated biomass of the species of the Barents Sea food-web

6. Why are these patterns important/essential to address the objectives?

The pattern of correlation can be interpreted directly to address the objective of the study since positive/negative correlations between prey and predators are indicative of bottom-up/top-down trophic controls. Persistent trophic control over time implies that the correlation values between the biomass time-series of two species are relatively stable over time (i.e., we don't observe large shifts between positive/negative correlations). Temporal variability in correlation values would imply that trophic controls in the Barents Sea food-web are not persistent.

2.2. Independent data

7. Where do the independent data originate from?

Primary production estimates were derived from the satellite measures of Chlorophyll-a (ICES, 2020). Time-series of herbivorous zooplankton, omnivorous zooplankton, pelagic fish, and demersal fish were derived from the data collected by the Working Group on the Integrated Assessment of the Barents Sea (ICES, 2020). Time-series of marine mammals were derived from data collected by the North Atlantic Marine Mammals Commission (NAMMCO – North Atlantic Marine Mammal Commission, 2021). Time-series of landings of pelagic and demersal fish were taken from the assessment of capelin and polar cod stocks, and from the assessment of cod, haddock and saith stocks, respectively. Time-series of marine mammals landings were taken from the NAMMCO data for minke whales and harp seals (<https://nammco.no/topics/common-minke-whale>, <https://nammco.no/topics/harp-seal>). Time-series of consumption by cod were taken from studies on stomach content analysis (Bjarte Bogstad, personal communication). Time-series of benthos and birds were reconstructed using the CaN model (Planque and Mullon, 2020).

8. What are the extent and resolution of the independent data?

The data used for the evaluation covered the whole Barents Sea area (Ozhigin et al., 2011). Measures of satellite data for chlorophyll-a is covering the time-period 1998-2018. All other time series cover the time-period 1988-2019.

9. How representative are the independent data of the ecological processes?

The independent data corresponds to the data collected during the Barents Sea survey in September every year. In other words, the independent biomass time series represent annual snapshots of the state of the Barents Sea in September. Thus, they are representative of the interannual fluctuations of biomass but not of the intra-annual fluctuations.

The independent diet data represent the biomass of the different preys of cod in stomach contents. The data available is representative of the temporal fluctuations of consumptions of cod and does not inform on the diet of other demersal fish species. Large uncertainties are present in diet derived from stomach content analysis (see e.g. Baker et al., 2014).

10. Are there estimates of independent data accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

Estimations of absolute values of chlorophyll-a concentrations derived from satellite data are associated with some uncertainties. However, these uncertainties are not communicated in the original publication from which the data was derived (ICES, 2020). Furthermore, satellite derived data may underestimate the primary production at depth, which adds a source of uncertainty. Another source of uncertainty is the fact that satellite derived data of chlorophyll-a is only available since 1998 but, we have reconstructed the past trajectories of the Barents Sea food-web for the time-period 1988-2019.

The independent data used to reconstruct past trajectories of the Barents Sea food-web were taken from stock assessment model outputs. These are outputs are provided with confidence intervals. We used the absolute values of these outputs as time-series for the CaN model and the confidence intervals to define the constraints for the reconstructions.

Data series on the biomass of benthos, marine mammals, and birds are not available. Thus, we reconstructed a large set of unconstrained possible trajectories for these groups. These reflect the uncertainty we have about these three trophospecies.

11. How are the independent data processed to represent the selected pattern and are assumptions made to derive these patterns from the data?

We assume that the independent data are representative of the interannual fluctuations of biomass for all species. We log₁₀ transformed all biomass data and

Model evaluation reporting form, OPE (Objective Patterns Evaluation)

assumed that the correlation estimated for log10-transformed data is a good-proxy for trophic control.

The time-series of marine mammals' catches were expressed in number of individuals. To express the total catch of marine mammals in tons/km², we applied a coefficient of 150kg for harp seal and 4000kg for minke whales. These values represent mean weights of harp seals and minke whales.

2.3. Model outputs

12. Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?

We used simulated biomass time-series of all trophospecies except phytoplankton.

13. Have the outputs been post-processed, and how?

Yes, we have log10 transformed the biomass data and estimated partial correlation based on the log10-transformed biomass time-series.

14. Are there estimates of model output accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

There is no estimates of accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty for single simulated trajectories of the Barents Sea food-web. However, we simulate a large number of possible trajectories with the NDND models that correspond to the same initial conditions. Thus, we can use biomass envelopes containing 50% or 95% of the simulated data as a measure of uncertainty.

15. Are additional assumptions made when deriving patterns from model outputs?

We assume that the estimated correlation value between log-transformed biomass is a good proxy to estimate trophic control between species.

3. Evaluation

3.1. Evaluation methodology

16. Are sanity checks conducted? If so, what is the method used?

- a. Which data and patterns are used for this?
- b. Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?

Data and patterns: in this NDND model application, we have defined HCRs for two trophospecies (pelagic and demersal fish). One sanity check of the simulation is to test if the fished biomass follows the HCR we have defined. Therefore, we plot the catch of each harvested trophospecies against the total stock biomass. The check is done

visually. The NDND model master equation is composed of different blocks representing the different input and losses of biomass. We estimate the biomass values of each block and reconstruct the biomass time-series. We then compared the simulated biomasses and the estimated ones. The difference between both time-series should be extremely close to 0.

Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?

Yes.

17. What is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from independent data with patterns from the model?
- a. What is the rationale for choosing this method?
 - b. How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?
 - c. Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?

We compare the biomass time-series simulated with the NDND model against historical time series reconstructed with a CaN model (Planque and Mullon, 2020). The simulated biomass needs to be in reasonable range around the historical time-series. For example, simulated biomass of demersal fish that is larger than the historical data by three or four orders of magnitude is considered unrealistic. To ensure this, we plotted violin plots of the simulated and observed data to ensure that both overlapped and to check that there was no large difference in biomass levels between simulations and observations. We also project the simulated and observed biomasses in the same principal component analysis (PCA) space to identify if the simulated and observed biomass overlap.

What is the rationale for choosing this method?

The aim of the study is to compare the patterns of trophic control between the simulated biomass and the observed data. We therefore check if there are temporal patterns in the simulated biomass. If there are no temporal patterns in our simulated biomass, it is not possible to compare them to historical biomass. We then check if the simulated biomasses include the historical biomass, which is a necessary condition for the model to be realistic with regards to the ecological patterns of interest.

How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?

The NDND model considers the uncertainties about the functioning of the food-web as a source of stochastic variability. Within a set of biological and physical limits of the ecosystem, we consider that all events are possible. It is also valid for the CaN model although it is further constrained by historical data. Furthermore, in the CaN model, historical data used to constrain the trajectories of the system are also characterized by uncertainties. We implemented them as a source of possible variability in the constraints based on historical time-series. It does not apply to the landings time series as catch data is relatively certain. Finally, input parameters for the NDND and CaN models are derived from the Metabolic Theory of Ecology and first principles.

Model evaluation reporting form, OPE (Objective Patterns Evaluation)

Consequently, the parameter values are relatively uncertain as they derived from theory. However, we did not address these uncertainties in this application.

Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?

No

18. Is there a threshold level (match between observed and modelled patterns) that can separate acceptable from unacceptable models?

If the historical dynamics of the system is not a solution of the model (i.e., there is a complete overlap between the reconstructed and the simulated biomass configurations), then our model is unacceptable.

19. How comparable are the patterns derived from the model and those derived from the independent data?

The simulated biomass represents annual estimates of biomass for the species of the Barents Sea food-web and the independent data represent annual snapshots of the stock at a given time in the year. We make the assumption that the annual estimates of biomass and the annual snapshots of biomass are equivalent in terms of temporal and spatial coverage and thus, we can compare them directly.

The comparison between the patterns derived from the model and the one derived from independent data is possible. However, the timespan considered in independent data is shorter (18 years) than the timespan of the patterns derived from the model outputs (26 years). Consequently, patterns derived from occurring at larger timescales than the time scale of the independent data cannot be compared.

3.2. Sensitivities

20. Has a model sensitivity analysis been performed, and how?

a. on the model structure?

b. on the model

a. On the model structure? No

b. On the model parametrization? No

21. Which elements are the modelled patterns most sensitive to?

- a. input parameters
- b. priors and assumptions
- c. structural elements

This has not been evaluated.

22. How sensitive are the modelled patterns to the choice of initial conditions, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution?

The sensitivity of the model to initial conditions has not been evaluated either. However, in our simulations, we have estimated a burn-in/spin-in period to derive the ecological pattern from simulation outputs that were independent from initial conditions. Therefore, we estimated the length of the burn-in/spin-in period based on the temporal autocorrelation.

23. How sensitive is the model evaluation to the independent data availability and uncertainty?

The sensitivity of the model evaluation to data availability and data uncertainty was not tested. Thus, we do not know how much the evaluation is affected by these factors. However, changes in input parameters may significantly affect the model outputs, and these input parameters, which are derived from the metabolic theory of ecology, remain uncertain. Thus, they may change the conclusion of the model evaluation. This applies also for the observational data used to set up the input parameters and the "reference" trajectories in the CaN model.

24. How much is the model evaluation constrained by computational or theoretical limits?

The model structure is simple, and the number of parameters is low, so the evaluation is not constrained by theoretical limits. In case of a future sensitivity analysis, the model evaluation may be limited by computational constraints. A single NDND simulation is relatively fast to perform. However, a sensitivity analysis implies to perform multiple simulations which can considerably increase the computational time. Also, NDND simulation outputs can be relatively large. Thus, multiple simulations require larger memory space.

25. How does the perceived performance of the model depend on the chosen evaluation methodology?

The model evaluation relies mainly on visual evaluation (empty polytope, violin plots, overlap in PCA-space, HCR, sanity check, etc.). The approach for the model evaluation is

subjective and its conclusions dependent on the model user. One way to improve the evaluation would be to add more factual elements such as the percentage of overlap between the simulated biomass and the observed biomass.

Another element that was discussed in the protocol but that we have not performed is a sensitivity analysis on the input parameters. Running a sensitivity analysis on parameters could strengthen our conclusions on the NDND model and its ability to reproduce the ecological patterns of the Barents Sea food-web.

References

- Baker, R., Buckland, A., Sheaves, M., 2014. Fish gut content analysis: robust measures of diet composition. *Fish and Fisheries* 15, 170–177. <https://doi.org/10.1111/faf.12026>
- Baranov, F.I., 1918. On the question of the biological basis of fisheries. *Izvestiya* 1, 81–128.
- Branch, T.A., 2009. Differences in predicted catch composition between two widely used catch equation formulations. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 66, 126–132. <https://doi.org/10.1139/F08-196>
- ICES, 2020. Working Group on the Integrated Assessments of the Barents Sea (WGIBAR). *ICES Scientific Reports* 2, 206. <https://doi.org/10.17895/ICES.PUB.5998>
- Johannesen, E., Ingvaldsen, R.B., Bogstad, B., Dalpadado, P., Eriksen, E., Gjøsæter, H., Knutsen, T., Skern-Mauritzen, M., Stiansen, J.E., 2012. Changes in Barents Sea ecosystem state, 1970–2009: climate fluctuations, human impact, and trophic interactions. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 69, 880–889. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fss046>
- Lindstrøm, U., Planque, B., Subbey, S., 2017. Multiple Patterns of Food Web Dynamics Revealed by a Minimal Non-deterministic Model. *Ecosystems* 20, 163–182. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10021-016-0022-y>
- Mullon, C., Fréon, P., Cury, P., Shannon, L., Roy, C., 2009. A minimal model of the variability of marine ecosystems. *Fish and Fisheries* 10, 115–131. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-2979.2008.00296.x>
- Ozhigin, V., Ingvaldsen, R., Loeng, H., Boitsov, V., Karsakov, A., 2011. Introduction to the Barents Sea, in: *The Barents Sea Ecosystem, Resources, Management. Half A Century of Russian-Norwegian Cooperation*. Tapir Academic Press, Trondheim, Norway, pp. 39–76.
- Planque, B., Lindstrøm, U., Subbey, S., 2014. Non-Deterministic Modelling of Food-Web Dynamics. *PLoS ONE* 9, e108243. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0108243>
- Planque, B., Mullon, C., 2020. Modelling chance and necessity in natural systems. *ICES J Mar Sci* 77, 1573–1588. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsz173>
- Sivel, E., Planque, B., Lindstrøm, U., Yoccoz, N.G., 2021. Multiple configurations and fluctuating trophic control in the Barents Sea food-web. *PLOS ONE* 16, e0254015. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0254015>

Name of the study:

The Nordic and Barents Seas Atlantis Model (NoBa) simulations to assess cumulative impact of fisheries and climate in the Norwegian and Barents Seas.

Author(s): Cecilie Hansen

Date: 2022

DOI (if applicable): 10.3389/fmars.2019.00668

Repository (e.g. GitHub): [Click or tap here to enter repository.](#)

Prior model developments and historical context:

The Nordic and Barents Seas Atlantis Model (NoBa) is a complex end-to-end model, covering the Nordic and Barents Seas by 60 polygons. This version of the model includes 53 ecosystem components, covering many trophic levels, from phytoplankton, through zooplankton, benthos, fish, seabirds and marine mammals, to the humans (represented by fisheries mortalities on the main commercial stocks). This NoBa version of the Atlantis framework (Fulton et al., 2011, Audzijonyte et al, 2017) was developed to specifically answer 'what if' questions, and explore ecosystem effects of cumulative impact, and has been used to explore effects of balanced harvesting, evaluate indicators used in the Barents Sea management plans, ecosystem based harvest control rules, and the combined effects of fisheries and climate change (this case study) (Nilsen et al., 2018, Hansen et al., 2021, Kaplan et al., 2020, Hansen et al., 2019). The case study was initiated through an EU-funded project; Climate change and European aquatic RESources (CERES), investigating how climate change and different management strategies would influence some of the large commercial stocks. The simulated scenarios followed the shared socio-economic pathways but specified to include potential changes in fishing mortalities and number of species harvested. The harvest rates were based on Pinnegar & Hamon, while the additional components being harvested were chosen based on their commercial value and interest.

1. Objectives

1.1. Context and motivations

1. What are the objectives of the model application

The aim of the study in Hansen et al. (2019a) was to explore how increased fishing mortality in combination with climate change would impact the vulnerability and/or structure of the Norwegian-Barents Sea ecosystem.

2. Why is the model suitable to address the objectives?

Atlantis is an end-to-end deterministic model constructed to explore ecosystem effects of cumulative pressures, such as climate and fisheries. The model gives output on biomasses, catches, diets and mortalities, to mention some. Given specified scenarios of climate change and harvest strategies, the model outputs can be used to quantify changes in structure of the ecosystem, relative to a baseline. From this, the vulnerability of the simulated ecosystem to combined climate change and harvest strategies could be assessed.

3. What would count as successful in achieving these objectives?

The simulations are successful if:

- 1. The historical period (1981-2017) is realistic. The biomass of most model components should follow historical patterns (if such are available) and stay within reasonable limits. For species that are of commercial interest, we add an uncertainty around the biomasses of 30%, which defines the limits. Other ecosystem components should stay within 0.5-1.5 x initial values, but we allow that biomass and/or numbers and individual weights of some ecosystem components are beyond their initial limits. This is done for most Atlantis models (Audzijonyte, 2017).*
- 2. The study is considered successful if we can gain knowledge on how the simulated ecosystem would respond to combined climate change and fisheries, in particular if there are any unexpected changes.*

1.2. Specific model setup

4. Are there any deviations from the original model description?
 - a. In the model assumptions?
 - b. In the model structure – submodels, variables, components, scales?
 - c. In the model details – parameter values, functional relationships
 - d. In the model forcing – initial conditions, boundary conditions, observation forcing, maps?

a. In the model assumptions?

Yes. The code version used is 6205, which can be downloaded from the Atlantis trunk.

b. In the model structure – submodels, variable, components, scale?

Yes. The fisheries module is included for these simulations. In the fisheries module, we've defined historical fishing patterns for the main commercial stocks (Northeast Arctic cod, Norwegian spring spawning herring, capelin, mackerel, haddock, golden and beaked redfish, Greenland halibut and prawns). From 2017 and onwards, the fishing mortality is given as a scalar of the fishing mortality at maximum sustainable yield (FMSY). The FMSY is calculated within the model system, increasing the fishing mortality (F) until collapse for a stock, while keeping the other constant. FMSY is then given as the top of the F-curve .

c. In the model details – parameter values, functional relationships

Yes. When adding fisheries mortalities to the commercial fish, natural mortality rates had to be adjusted accordingly for these components

d. In the model forcing – initial conditions, boundary conditions, observation forcing, maps?

Yes. As only one year of forcing (1981) was applied in Hansen et al., 2019b, we had to add a time-series of forcing to explore the climate change. This time-series was constructed from physical ocean model simulations for the period 1981-2068. In addition, fisheries mortalities were forced (see above), these were calculated based on ICES working group reports (ICES, 2018a, b). In addition, zooplankton growth forcing is applied in the simulations, to create variability around each of the scenarios.

2. Patterns

2.1. Selected patterns

5. Which ecological patterns are used for the model evaluation?

a. Temporal patterns – cycles, shifts, trends, variability, autocorrelation

We used the biomass patterns for the pelagic and demersal fish and for the lower-trophic levels (aggregated into functional groups; Hansen et al., 2019b), including several model components) for the model evaluation.

b. Spatial patterns – synchrony, travelling waves, patchiness, autocorrelation

For these simulations, we did not take into consideration spatial aspects.

c. Structural, functional patterns – diversity, biomass ratio, integrated production, diet, traits

For the evaluation, we used temporal correlation between observed values of biomass and the simulated biomasses for the the demersal fish and the pelagic fish.

6. Why are these patterns important/essential to address the objectives?

If NoBa is not realistic for the historical period, it would require re-tuning of the model. The aim of the study was to explore the combined impact of fisheries and climate scenarios in a projected future (following RCP 4.5), and if the model had no skill of the past, it would be less likely that it had any skill in the future either. Therefore, the simulation of historical ecological patterns that are close to those emerging from observations are important to determine if the model would be capable of simulating realistic patterns under scenarized climate and fishing pressures.

2.2. Independent data

7. Where do the independent data originate from?

Observations used for evaluations were time-series of biomasses and catches from stock assessments (ICES 2017, 2018) of the large commercial stocks (herring, mackerel, blue whiting, capelin, Northeast Arctic cod, haddock, Greenland halibut, golden and beaked redfish). The model is forced by mortality rates from catch statistics for the same stocks, hence model evaluation and input data are partly dependent upon each other.

8. What are the extent and resolution of the independent data?

The data used in the model evaluation covered the whole Barents and Norwegian Seas, on a yearly timescale for the period 1981-2017.

9. How representative are the independent data of the ecological processes?

The data are annual estimates of the main commercial stocks in the Norwegian and Barents Seas. Hence, they give a good overview of the year-to-year variation.

10. Are there estimates of independent data accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

Yes, the time-series from the stock assessments are given with uncertainty. In the study, a general uncertainty of 20% was added to the time-series when comparing to historical biomasses of demersal and pelagic fish from NoBa.

11. How are the independent data processed to represent the selected pattern and are assumptions made to derive these patterns from the data?

To represent functional groups, the biomasses and catches were merged into three groups: demersal, pelagic and lower-trophic levels. We include only the species in NoBa that we had assessment data for and assume that these are representative for the functional groups.

2.3. Model outputs

12. Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?

Biomass time-series of the commercial stocks (cod, haddock, Greenland halibut, golden redfish, beaked redfish, other demersals, large demersals, mackerel, blue whiting, herring, capelin in addition to , polar cod) and of the lower trophic level species; mesozooplankton, prawns, mesopelagic fish, jellyfish, small and large zooplankton.

13. Have the outputs been post-processed, and how?

They have been added together to form functional groups; pelagic, demersal, harvested lower trophic levels and non-harvested lower trophic levels.

14. Are there estimates of model output accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

The biomass development from the simulations (including 14 different runs for each scenario) was compared to the biomass development in the observed time-series, to provide estimates of trends and biomass levels. In Hansen et al. (2019b), estimated individual weight of each of the functional groups was compared the realized weight in the components, and it was found that 75% of these were within acceptable limits.

15. Are additional assumptions made when deriving patterns from model outputs?

Yes. A conversion rate from nitrate to wet weight is applied, this value is the same for all species.

3. Evaluation

3.1. Evaluation methodology

16. Are sanity checks conducted? If so, what is the method used?

- a. Which data and patterns are used for this?
- b. Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?

a. Data and patterns: time-series of zooplankton were used to create variability around each scenario. This was applied to the growth rate of mesozooplankton. A visual sanity check was performed to make sure that the mesozooplankton biomass responded to the forcing.

b. For many of the components included in NoBa, we don't have long time series, and rather make sure that they follow expected seasonal patterns (e.g. phytoplankton), stay within reasonable levels (zooplankton, jellyfish) and that their numbers and weights (fish, seabirds, mammals) do not go above/below 0.5-1.5 times their initial values when run towards equilibrium unless other ranges has been observed (see Hansen et al., 2019a).

17. What is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from independent data with patterns from the model?

- a. What is the rationale for choosing this method?
- b. How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?
- c. Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?

Correlations were performed to compare the simulated and observed historical patterns. Catch levels for corresponding components in model and observations were calculated/gathered and compared (in numbers/fractions) per functional group. Patterns (fraction of catch per functional group) were visually compared (but were also given in numbers).

18. Is there a threshold level (match between observed and modelled patterns) that can separate acceptable from unacceptable models?

We have not defined such a level in this study. However, if both biomass levels and patterns were not comparable to those from the observations (no correlation, opposite trends, weights and/or biomasses outside 0.5-1.5 initial levels or above/below observed levels), we would not consider the model fit for purpose.

19. How comparable are the patterns derived from the model and those derived from the independent data?

Both the pelagic and demersal functional groups diverged in terms of biomass for the historical period before year 2000. After year 2000, the two time-series (simulated and observed) overlap. The trends for the historical period show the same development, more so for the demersal fish than the pelagic fish. The boom and bust behavior of the capelin stock was not captured in NoBa, resulting in a larger difference in biomass and pattern for the pelagic functional group.

3.2. Sensitivities

20. Has a model sensitivity analysis been performed, and how?

- a. on the model structure?
- b. on the model

Not for this study.

21. Which elements are the modelled patterns most sensitive to?

- a. input parameters
- b. priors and assumptions
- c. structural elements

The model is sensitive to perturbations at the zooplankton level (Hansen et al., 2019b), which was the reason for why we chose to force the mesozooplankton growth rates to create a solution room around the scenarios. The sensitivity to parameter perturbations depends on which trophic level the component belongs to, where the lower trophic levels respond stronger to parameter perturbations compared to the higher trophic levels.

22. How sensitive are the modelled patterns to the choice of initial conditions, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution?

The sensitivity of the model to the initial conditions and spin-up time has not been formally evaluated. However, there is a burn-in of 24 years. The sensitivity of the NoBa model to the length of the spin-up period was tested at an early stage of the model development (not published). The model is known to be little sensitive to initial biomass levels. The model does not apply boundary conditions, and the spatial and temporal resolution has not been changed. The sensitivity to spatial and temporal resolution has not been tested.

23. How sensitive is the model evaluation to the independent data availability and uncertainty?

The model has thousands of parameters, and in previous studies (Nilsen et al., 2020) we have observed that the more data-limited stocks are not responding similarly to harvest patterns compared to the more data rich stocks.

24. How much is the model evaluation constrained by computational or theoretical limits?

The model is relatively computationally heavy and produces a massive amount of output. It is to some degree constrained by computational limits due to this. We have still not been successful in finding an improved method for comparing the state of the ecosystem within the model to the observed, to find if the model is within the boundaries of the observed system.

25. How does the perceived performance of the model depend on the chosen evaluation methodology?

As we did not define specific ranges/limits for what we would define as acceptable ranges of the biomass and catch development in the model, the performance relies heavily on the methodology that we have chosen.

References

- Hansen, C., Nash, R.D.M., Drinkwater, K.F., Hjøllø, S.S., 2019a. Management Scenarios Under Climate Change – A Study of the Nordic and Barents Seas. *Front. Mar. Sci.*, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2019.00668>
- Hansen, C., Drinkwater, K.F., Jähkel, A., Fulton, E.A., Gorton, R., Skern-Mauritzen, M. 2019b. Sensitivity of the Norwegian and Barents Sea Atlantis end-to-end ecosystem model to parameter perturbations of key species. *PlosONE.*, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0210419>
- ICES (2018). Report of the Arctic Fisheries Working Group (AFWG). ICES; 18–24 April 2018. p. 534.

Model evaluation reporting form, OPE (Objective Patterns Evaluation)

ICES (2017). ICES. Report of the Working Group on Widely Distributed Stocks (WGWIDE). ICES; 30 August -5 September 2017. p. 994.

Name of the study:

Evaluation of NorCPM1 as a driver for Ecosystem Reconstructions and Predictions in the Barents Sea

Author(s): Filippa Fransner

Date: 2022

DOI (if applicable): [Click or tap here to enter DOI.](#)

Repository (e.g. GitHub): [Click or tap here to enter repository.](#)

Prior model developments and historical context:

The Norwegian Climate Prediction Model (NorCPM1, Bethke et al., 2021) is designed to create climate reconstructions and seasonal-to-decadal predictions. It is based on the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM, Bentsen et al., 2013, Tjiputra et al., 2013), with components representing the atmosphere, the physical ocean, the biogeochemical ocean, sea ice and land. It has a 1° horizontal resolution in the ocean, and 2° resolution in the atmosphere. For climate reconstructions, which also are called reanalyses, NorCPM1 applies an Ensemble Kalman Filter that assimilated anomalies of observational data of sea surface temperature (SST) and as well as temperature and salinity profiles (Counillon et al., 2014, 2016; Wang et al., 2016, 2017) into the model. This brings the model state closer to the actual state of the climate, and thus reconstructs the past variability of the ocean and the atmosphere. The reanalyses are used as initial conditions for seasonal-to-decadal predictions, which are run freely for one and ten years, respectively. In addition to the reanalyses and the predictions, a historical run is performed, where the only applied forcing is historical solar forcing, land use, concentrations and emissions of greenhouse gases and aerosols. The historical run is used as a benchmark when evaluating the hindcasts and the reanalyses with observational data.

NorCPM1 is one of several climate prediction models that participate in the coupled Model Intercomparison Project 6 (CMIP6) Decadal Climate Prediction Project (DCPP). The simulations prepared CMIP6 DCPP with NorCPM1 consist of one historical run, two reanalysis products and two decadal climate hindcast products. The historical run covers the period of 1850-2014, and has been run with 30 members without data assimilation. The reanalyses also consist of 30 members each and have been run between 1950-2019 with monthly data assimilation. The first reanalysis (dcpa-assim1) performs weakly coupled data assimilation and uses the period of 1980-2010 as a reference climatology, while the second one (dcpa-assim2) performs strongly coupled data assimilation, where the sea ice is updated during the assimilation step, and uses 1950-2010 as a reference climatology. The ten-years long hindcasts, dcpa-hindcast1 and dcpa-hindcast2, are started every year between 1960 and 2019 and consist of ten members each. While dcpa-hindcast1 uses output from dcpa-assim1 as initial conditions, dcpa-hindcast2 uses output from dcpa-assim2. For more details the reader is referred to Bethke et al. (2021).

1. Objectives

1.1. Context and motivations

1. What are the objectives of the model application

The objective of this specific application of NorCPM1 is to use its output as physical and biogeochemical forcing for ecological models, to create interannual-to-decadal reconstructions and predictions of the ecological state of the Barents Sea.

2. Why is the model suitable to address the objectives?

NorCPM1 is suitable for the application as it is a model designed for creating climate reconstructions and predictions.

3. What would count as successful in achieving these objectives?

We consider the model to be successful in achieving the objectives if it is able to reproduce interannual variations in important ecosystem drivers, such as temperature, salinity, nutrient and phytoplankton concentration. Because we are interested in the variability, we do not consider any offsets between the modelled fields and the observations. Eventual offsets in the modelled fields can be handled with bias correction.

1.2. Specific model setup

4. Are there any deviations from the original model description?

- a. In the model assumptions?
- b. In the model structure – submodels, variables, components, scales?
- c. In the model details – parameter values, functional relationships
- d. In the model forcing – initial conditions, boundary conditions, observation forcing, maps?

We use the simulations prepared for CMIP6 DCPP, and there are therefore no deviations of the model nor the simulations from the model description in Bethke et al (in revision).

2. Patterns

2.1. Selected patterns

5. Which ecological patterns are used for the model evaluation?

For this specific application we consider interannual variations of physical and biogeochemical properties (temperature, salinity, and concentration of nitrate, phosphate, silicate and phytoplankton carbon) in the Atlantic Water, which following Olsen et al., 2003 is defined as the region between 72-73°N in the BSO. We are primarily

focusing on the Atlantic Water because it makes up an important part of the water body of the Barents Sea. As primary production mainly takes place in surface waters, we further evaluate the model's capability to reproduce interannual variations in surface (0-25 m) and deep (100-300m) waters.

6. Why are these patterns important/essential to address the objectives?

To evaluate whether NorCPM1 can be used as a driver for ecosystem reconstructions and predictions, it is essential to verify its ability to reproduce interannual to decadal variations in these ecosystem drivers (under point 5).

2.2. Independent data

7. Where do the independent data originate from?

Observational data of chlorophyll (used as proxy for phytoplankton carbon), nitrate, phosphate and silicate concentration, temperature and salinity, come from the Fugløya-Bjørnøya (FB) transect in the Barents Sea Opening, sampled by the Institute of Marine Research (IMR).

8. What are the extent and resolution of the independent data?

FB, stretches between 70.5-74.3°N and 19.2-20.0°E, and is visited up to five times per year. Up to 6 stations per latitude are sampled.

9. How representative are the independent data of the ecological processes?

Data of temperature, salinity, and nutrient concentrations are direct measures of the properties that we want to evaluate. Data of chlorophyll concentration is only a proxy for phytoplankton (carbon) concentration, as the chlorophyll:carbon ratio can vary. The representativeness of the monthly means that have been created from the data can be questioned, as sampling time within a month can vary between years. Although located in the center of the Barents Sea opening, it is possible that there occasionally can be intrusions of coastal and arctic waters in the latitude band of 72-73 (Olsen et al., 2003), and it is therefore possible that this region is not always representative for the Atlantic Water.

10. Are there estimates of independent data accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

No information is provided in the dataset.

11. How are the independent data processed to represent the selected pattern and are assumptions made to derive these patterns from the data?

As the exact position, sampling depth and month are varying slightly from year to year, the observational data was first gridded into latitude bands of 0.1 degrees, fixed depth levels (0,5,10,20,30,50,75,100,125,150,200,150, 300m) and monthly time intervals. Because the section is not sampled every month, seasonal means for the winter (JFM), spring (AMJ), summer (JAS), and autumn (OND), were thereafter calculated for each year from the gridded monthly means. For surface and deep water time series, a mean was calculated over the upper 25 and lower 100-300 meters, respectively. Finally, a mean was calculated over the region 72-73°N to get one timeseries for the Atlantic Water. The chlorophyll (Chl)

concentration is transformed to carbon (C) concentration by using a constant C:Chl ratio of 1:20.

2.3. Model outputs

12. Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?

We use model output of monthly mean temperature, salinity, and concentrations of phosphate, nitrate, silicate and phytoplankton carbon.

13. Have the outputs been post-processed, and how?

We calculated ensemble means of output of monthly mean temperature, salinity, and nutrient and phytoplankton carbon concentrations from three different simulations; the analysis, the hindcasts and the historical run. To be compatible with the processed observational data, seasonal means for the winter, spring, summer and autumn for surface (0-25m) and deep (100-300m) waters are calculated.

14. Are there estimates of model output accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

The model has been run with several members, or realisations (i.e., The historical run and the reanalyses are performed in 30 realizations, and the hindcasts are performed in 10 realizations), starting at slightly different times. This gives an estimate of the impact of the initialization date, and stochastic climate processes, on the model results. The idea is that when averaging over the ten members, this uncertainty is reduced.

15. Are additional assumptions made when deriving patterns from model outputs?

The relatively coarse resolution (1 degree) of the model makes it impossible to extract data at the same locations as the observational data. Data from grid cells that are closest possible to the FB-section are extracted. For the region 72-73 N there is only one corresponding grid cell from the model. It is important to note that the output from this grid cell corresponds to a spatial mean over the whole grid cell.

3. Evaluation

3.1. Evaluation methodology

16. Are sanity checks conducted? If so, what is the method used?

- a. Which data and patterns are used for this?
- b. Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?

A sanity check of the model has been performed in the model description paper (Bethke et al., 2021).

17. What is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from independent data with patterns from the model?

- a. What is the rationale for choosing this method?
- b. How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?
- c. Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?

Time series of modelled AW temperature, salinity, phytoplankton and nutrient concentrations, from surface and deep waters, are compared to the same observational quantities by anomaly correlations and root mean squared error (RMSE). To reduce noise in the timeseries we apply a four-year running mean before the comparison. As we are interested in interannual to decadal variations, we remove the mean from both the observational and modelled timeseries. Before calculating the correlation between the time series, we also perform a detrending. This is to remove the signal of climate change, which otherwise can result in strong correlations between the modelled and observed timeseries.

18. Is there a threshold level (match between observed and modelled patterns) that can separate acceptable from unacceptable models?

We consider a correlation that is significantly different from zero, and that is significantly greater than the correlation between historical run and the observations, to be skillfull. The comparison with the historical run is done to ensure that the skill does not come from any external forcing, and is purely a result of internal variability. The significance test is performed calculating 95% confidence intervals with a Fisher's transformation. The comparison with the skill of the historical run is to ensure that the skill comes from the dynamical system itself, and not from the external forcing. In addition, we require that the RMSE should be less than 80% of the standard deviation of the timeseries (that has been detrended and demeaned).

19. How comparable are the patterns derived from the model and those derived from the independent data?

Comparing measured and modelled temperature, salinity, and nutrient concentrations are relatively strait forward per se. However, in the evaluation we perform in this example we identify especially two pitfalls.

The first one is related to the relatively sparse sampling. A sampling frequency of five times per year is not enough to construct annual means. This is why we focused on summer and winter means. We decided not to look at spring and autumn as these are periods of rapid change, and variations in the time of sampling from year to year can induce spurious variability. One can also question if the discrete samples can be compared to the model output that has a 1 degree horizontal resolution. This is dealt with in the meridional direction as we construct a mean of the observations over 72-73 °N.

The second pitfall is the use of chlorophyll as a proxy for phytoplankton carbon concentration. The chlorophyll to carbon ratio is known to be highly variable, especially at high latitudes. To get an idea of the model's performance when it comes to simulation of phytoplankton dynamics it is therefore good to use also other proxies. One such proxy that can be derived from the other measured quantities is the nutrient consumption, i.e., the difference between the winter and summer nutrient concentrations.

3.2. Sensitivities

20. Has a model sensitivity analysis been performed, and how?

- a. on the model structure?
- b. on the model

Not for this specific application.

21. Which elements are the modelled patterns most sensitive to?

- a. input parameters
- b. priors and assumptions
- c. structural elements

N/A

22. How sensitive are the modelled patterns to the choice of initial conditions, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution?

The model has undergone an extensive spin-up prior to the experiments, and no significant model drift is present in the model results.

For the hindcasts the initial conditions are of great importance as wrong initial conditions will degrade the predictive skill. For the analysis, the initial conditions are less important as observational data is assimilated each month to bring the model as close to reality as possible.

Because it is a global model there are no spatial boundary conditions. The only boundary conditions that are used is the external forcing, i.e., atmospheric CO₂ and aerosol concentration. The sensitivity to these boundary conditions is eliminated by comparing the skill of the hindcast and analysis to the skill of the historical run.

It is well known that the results of climate models are sensitive to the spatial and temporal resolution. In our case, NorCPM1 do not resolve mesoscale processes. The absence of mesoscale processes tends to make the model results too diffuse, for example the northward heat transport by the North Atlantic current and the Norwegian Atlantic current is degraded. This is, however, nothing we can test in our application due to lack of computational resources.

23. How sensitive is the model evaluation to the independent data availability and uncertainty?

The model evaluation can only provide information of the model's performance within the time period and geographical range of observational data. In our case, an evaluation of the model in the Barents Sea Opening does not imply that it is valid for the rest of the Barents Sea. This is however the only region of the Barents Sea with a frequent recurring sampling, and therefore the best option available. There is also the Vardo N transect. However, it is only

visited twice a year, making it difficult to get a reasonable estimate of the amplitude of the seasonal cycle.

Because we do not have uncertainty estimates on the observational data, we cannot estimate its impact on the evaluation.

24. How much is the model evaluation constrained by computational or theoretical limits?

The model is computationally heavy and produces a lot of output, meaning that it is difficult to produce a large number of different simulations for sensitivity analyses.

25. How does the perceived performance of the model depend on the chosen evaluation methodology?

The use of anomaly correlation, and RMSE of the demeaned timeseries, as measures for the skill has been taken with care. This does not say anything about the offset between the modelled and measured quantities; even though there is a high correlation between the modelled and observed interannual variations, there might still be a bias in the absolute quantities. For example, the modelled winter temperature is on average 2 degrees lower than that of the observations. For this specific application, these offsets can be minimized by bias correction.

References

- Bentsen, M., Bethke, I., Debernard, J. B., Iversen, T., Kirkevåg, A., Seland, Ø., Drange, H., Roelandt, C., Seierstad, I. A., Hoose, C., and Kristjánsson, J. E. (2013). The Norwegian Earth System Model, NorESM1-M Part 1: Description and basic evaluation of the physical climate. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 6(3):687–720.
- Bethke, I., Wang, Y., Counillon, F., Keenlyside, N., Kimmritz, M., Fransner, F., ... & Eldevik, T. (2021). NorCPM1 and its contribution to CMIP6 DCP. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 14(11), 7073-7116.
- Counillon, F., Bethke, I., Keenlyside, N., Bentsen, M., Bertino, L., and Zheng, F. (2014). Seasonal-to-decadal predictions with the ensemble Kalman filter and the Norwegian Earth System Model: a twin experiment. *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, 66(1):21074.
- Counillon, F., Keenlyside, N., Bethke, I., Wang, Y., Billeau, S., Shen, M. L., and Bentsen, M. (2016). Flow-dependent assimilation of sea surface temperature in isopycnal coordinates with the Norwegian Climate Prediction Model. *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, 68(1):32437.
- Olsen, A., Johannessen, T., and Rey, F. (2003) On the nature of the factors that control spring bloom development at the entrance to the Barents Sea and their interannual variability, *Sarsia*, 88:6, 379-393, DOI: [10.1080/00364820310003145](https://doi.org/10.1080/00364820310003145)
- Tjiputra, J. F., Roelandt, C., Bentsen, M., Lawrence, D. M., Lorentzen, T., Schwinger, J., Seland, Ø., and Heinze, C. (2013). Evaluation of the carbon cycle components in the

Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM). *Geoscientific Model Development*, 6(2):301–325.

Wang, Y., Counillon, F., and Bertino, L. (2016). Alleviating the bias induced by the linear analysis update with an isopycnal ocean model. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 142(695):1064–1074.

Wang, Y., Counillon, F., Bethke, I., Keenlyside, N., Bocquet, M., and Lin Shen, M. (2017). Optimising assimilation of hydrographic profiles into isopycnal ocean models with ensemble data assimilation. *Ocean Modelling*, 114:33 – 44.

Name of the study:

an Individual Based Model (IBM) used to quantify uncertainties in the estimates of mean biomass of the copepod *Calanus finmarchicus* as a function of sampling design

Author(s): Morten D. Skogen

Date: 2022

DOI (if applicable): doi.org/10.3354/meps13574

Repository (e.g. GitHub): [Click or tap here to enter repository.](#)

Prior model developments and historical context:

*The NORwegian ECOlogical Model system End-To-End (NORWECOM.E2E), a coupled physical, chemical, biological model system (Skogen et al., 1995; Skogen and Sjøiland, 1998), was originally developed to study primary production, nutrient budgets and dispersion of particles such as fish larvae and pollution in the North Sea. Later, the biogeochemical part of the model was set up in an area covering the Nordic and Barents Sea in offline mode i.e., using ocean physics from an ocean circulation model as forcing. The model has been extended with a number of Individual Based Models (IBMs) for key species in these areas (Aarflot et al., in press; Hansen et al., 2021; Hjøllø et al., 2012; Utne et al., 2012), and with a module to project ocean acidification (Skogen et al., 2014). Together, this makes the model a flexible tool to study and quantify ecosystem dynamics and interactions. The motivation for the current study developed from earlier studies in which observations of the mesozooplankton *C. finmarchicus* in the Norwegian Sea were compared to model simulations. Such exercise has proven difficult due to the high variability in space and time of the empirical observations (Hjøllø et al., 2021; Skogen et al., 2021).*

1. Objectives

1.1. Context and motivations

1. What are the objectives of the model application

*The objective of this application of the NORWECOM.E2E model is to simulate the mesoscale spatial and temporal dynamics of zooplankton and, using these simulations, to quantify the uncertainty in the mean biomass estimates of *C. finmarchicus* as a function of the sampling design. Field investigations of zooplankton in the Norwegian Sea have shown a decrease in biomass from the 1990s into the 2000s, with a stabilization and slight increase after 2009 (Huse et al., 2012; ICES, 2020). Annual biomass estimates are based on a varying number of plankton net hauls in May. Zooplankton distributions are spatially patchy (e.g. Fasham, 1978; Young et al., 2009) and seasonally variable, with a strong increase in biomass in May due to rapid individual growth (e.g. Hjøllø et al., 2012). Due to the observed patchiness, biomass estimates are believed to be very sensitive to the field sampling design. The ecosystem model NORWECOM.E2E is used to resample zooplankton biomass in silico to quantify the sensitivity of biomass estimates to the sampling design.*

2. Why is the model suitable to address the objectives?

*The NORWECOM.E2E couples a high-resolution ocean dynamics model, a NPZD (Nutrients, Phytoplankton, Zooplankton, Detritus) model and a full life-cycle Individual Based Model for *C. finmarchicus* (Hjøllø et al., 2012; Huse et al., 2018). The *C. finmarchicus* IBM has previously been evaluated through a comparison with field data in Hjøllø et al. (2012) and Skaret et al. (2014). The model is therefore expected to produce mesoscale dynamical patterns of the distribution of *C. finmarchicus* that are sufficiently realistic to evaluate the plankton sampling design.*

3. What would count as successful in achieving these objectives?

The study is considered successful if it is possible to assess the sensitivity of zooplankton biomass estimates to the in situ sampling, using in silico sampling as a proxy.

1.2. Specific model setup

4. Are there any deviations from the original model description?
 - a. In the model assumptions?
 - b. In the model structure – submodels, variables, components, scales?
 - c. In the model details – parameter values, functional relationships
 - d. In the model forcing – initial conditions, boundary conditions, observation forcing, maps?

The study has been performed using the NPZD and the C. finmarchicus IBM modules of the NORWECOM.E2E model version: b924131. The code can be downloaded from <https://git.imr.no/norwecome2e/norwecome2e>. The model is fully described in Hjøllø et al (2012) and Huse et al. (2018). Compared to the published version of the model, structure, assumptions and forcing are unchanged, however there have been some changes in model details regarding parameters values and relationships.

2. Patterns

2.1. Selected patterns

5. Which ecological patterns are used for the model evaluation?

The model is evaluated by a comparison to observed seasonal patterns and observed long-term mean spatial biomass in the Norwegian Sea in May.

6. Why are these patterns important/essential to address the objectives?

These patterns are used to assess zooplankton biomass in the Norwegian Sea. Before assessing the importance of temporal and spatial patterns, we need to ensure that the model is doing a good job in reproducing the level and seasonal development of biomass in the period of interest. These patterns are important as the sensitivity of the mean biomass to the sampling design are to be investigated through a perturbation of sampling stations in time and space which will drive the uncertainty estimate.

2.2. Independent data

7. Where do the independent data originate from?

The field data on zooplankton biomasses was collected by the Norwegian Institute of Marine Research (IMR) and later extracted from IMR databases. The dataset is restricted to only cover the Norwegian Sea (west of 18°E and for 60-72°N) for the period 1995 to 2004.

8. What are the extent and resolution of the independent data?

*The zooplankton biomass samples are collected by WP-2 nets (Fraser, 1966) with an opening area of 0.25m² and a modified mesh-size of 180 µm. The WP-2 nets were hauled vertically from 200m (or near the seabed in shallow areas) to the ocean surface. The unit is dry weight per unit surface area. Size-fractionated biomass is estimated for all samples using the size-fractions: 0.18-1mm, 1-2 mm, and > 2 mm. Estimates of observed *Calanus finmarchicus* biomass for each month are calculated as arithmetic mean over all relevant stations, using *C. finmarchicus* content of 50%, 70% and 0% of the size-fractions 0.18-1mm, 1-2 mm, and > 2 mm, respectively (W. Melle, Inst. of Marine Research, pers. comm.). Dry weight biomass is converted to carbon using C/DW-ratio = 0.45 (Brey et al., 2010). Number of stations varies from 22 in 1997 to 108 in 1999.*

9. How representative are the independent data of the ecological processes?

*We know from previous studies that the spatial distribution of *C. finmarchicus* is highly patchy (Basedow et al., 2006). In addition, the temporal changes in size and stage of the copepods are rapid, reflecting the intense spring season with length of different life stages on the order of days, and individuals undergoing their whole life cycle in 22-59 days, depending on temperature and food concentration (Campbell et al., 2001). For these reasons, we are not fully confident that the plankton monitoring data robustly represents the patterns (interannual variations & spatial distribution patterns). The aim of this modelling application is to evaluate the robustness of estimated interannual variations in biomass based on observational data.*

10. Are there estimates of independent data accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

No. At present, observation-based biomass estimates are provided without uncertainty.

11. How are the independent data processed to represent the selected pattern and are assumptions made to derive these patterns from the data?

The mean spatial biomass is computed as the arithmetic mean of the observations under the assumption that they are representative for the large-scale patterns.

2.3. Model outputs

12. Which model outputs are used for the evaluation?

*Due to the numerically vast numbers of *C. finmarchicus* each modelled individual is assumed to represent a varying number of identical siblings following the super-individual (SI) approach (Scheffer, 1995). Model fields (all SI) are stored every second day, and *C. finmarchicus* biomass and abundance are calculated from all stage CI-CVI*

individuals in the upper 200 m. Model estimates of mean biomass was produced using arithmetic means of biomass from observational locations and date in the nearest corresponding point in the model. Note that the in silico and in situ volumes sampled are different as the model represents a mean over a gridcell (4x4km) while the opening of the WP2 net is only 0.25m²

13. Have the outputs been post-processed, and how?

The super individuals only occupy one single point in space and have no areal extent. Therefore, each SI are smoothed horizontally assuming a bi-normal distribution and a radius of 5 grid cells (approximately 100 km). These individual distributions are then added up to produce one 2D depth integrated (0-200m) field for each copepod stage.

14. Are there estimates of model output accuracy, precision, bias, or uncertainty?

No. For a process rich model uncertainty is primarily from the lack of process understanding and the model parameterization of these in addition to the lack of proper forcing, initial and boundary fields. For such models a full estimate of model accuracy is not possible. Assuming the presence of precise estimates for state variables model biases can be calculated, but that is not the case for the studied ecological patterns.

15. Are additional assumptions made when deriving patterns from model outputs?

The model uses Carbon as a state variable, and a Carbon:dry weight ratio of 0.45 (Brey et al., 2010) is assumed.

3. Evaluation

3.1. Evaluation methodology

16. Are sanity checks conducted? If so, what is the method used?

- a. Which data and patterns are used for this?
- b. Does this apply to patterns that are not otherwise evaluated for this model application?

*When running the model for several years, the population should neither explode nor become extinct. Rather, it should show a relatively stable winter and summer biomass. *C. finmarchicus* total summer biomass within the Norwegian Seas should be on the order of 10MT carbon, with a seasonal pattern that shows a lower biomass in April/May after spawning of the new generation in spring (Skjoldal, 2004).*

17. What is the methodology used to compare ecological patterns derived from independent data with patterns from the model?
- What is the rationale for choosing this method?
 - How are observational and/or model output uncertainties handled?
 - Does the methodology rely on specific assumptions?

The long term mean biomass in May has been compared visually between model and observations. The same approach has been on the evaluation of the seasonal pattern with a special focus on the timing of the appearance of the new generation in spring.

These comparisons are consistent with the objective of the study, which is to evaluate the sensitivity of zooplankton biomass estimates to the sampling design. Uncertainties in these estimates are potentially large due - to a low representativity in the observations - and the model has been evaluated on a coarser level.

18. Is there a threshold level (match between observed and modelled patterns) that can separate acceptable from unacceptable models?

*No. However, large sensitivity and inter annual variability between the time-series on the order of the interannual variability, indicates that the observations are non-informative about the year-to-year changes in *C. finmarchicus* biomass.*

19. How comparable are the patterns derived from the model and those derived from the independent data?

*The model has a horizontal resolution of 20x20 km, while observed patchiness of *C. finmarchicus* of ~17km has been reported (Basedow et al., 2006). The observations are from field sampling with WP2 nets which have an opening of 0.25m².*

3.2. Sensitivities

20. Has a model sensitivity analysis been performed, and how?
- on the model structure?
 - on the model

A sensitivity analysis for a few key-parameters is presented in Hjøllo et al. (2012). With the high number of parameters and state variables, a full sensitivity analysis for the model is not achievable. The focus of the sensitivity analysis in Hjøllo et al. (2012) was on the initial values of behavioural traits and the number of super individuals.

21. Which elements are the modelled patterns most sensitive to?

- a. input parameters
- b. priors and assumptions
- c. structural elements

The modelled patterns depend on both forcing, initial fields and process formulation and parameterization. The relative sensitivity of these has not been quantified.

22. How sensitive are the modelled patterns to the choice of initial conditions, boundary conditions, spatial and temporal resolution?

These sensitivities have not been quantified.

23. How sensitive is the model evaluation to the independent data availability and uncertainty?

The hypothesis is that the model evaluation is sensitive to the data availability as the study objective is to question the representativeness assumption of the observations. However, this sensitivity is challenging, if not impossible to quantify.

24. How much is the model evaluation constrained by computational or theoretical limits?

The model is complex, with a high number of components, functional relationships, and parameters. If a full evaluation or sensitivity analysis was to be run, the dimension of the exercise would be very large and the required computing time to do it would be, at present, infeasible.

25. How does the perceived performance of the model depend on the chosen evaluation methodology?

*The 40, 70, 0% fractions are unpublished means based on long term experience. This is known to vary in space and time. However, as each sample is not made up on species, this is the only way to transfer from observed total biomass to modelled *C. finmarchicus* biomass.*

References

Aarflot, J.M., Hjøllø, S.S., Strand, E., Skogen, M.D., in press. An individual based *Calanus hyperboreus* model for the Nordic seas. Progress In Oceanography.

- Basedow, S.L., Edvardsen, A., Tande, K.S., 2006. Spatial patterns of surface blooms and recruitment dynamics of *Calanus finmarchicus* in the NE Norwegian Sea. *Journal of Plankton Research* 28, 1181–1190. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbl048>
- Brey, T., Müller-Wiegmann, C., Zittier, Z.M.C., Hagen, W., 2010. Body composition in aquatic organisms — A global data bank of relationships between mass, elemental composition and energy content. *Journal of Sea Research* 64, 334–340. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seares.2010.05.002>
- Campbell, R., Wagner, M., Teegarden, G., Boudreau, C., Durbin, E., 2001. Growth and development rates of the copepod *Calanus finmarchicus* reared in the laboratory. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 221, 161–183. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps221161>
- Fasham, M.J.R., 1978. The statistical and mathematical analysis of plankton patchiness. *Oceanogr. Mar. Biol. ann. Review* 16, 43–79.
- Fraser, J.H., 1966. Zooplankton Sampling. *Nature* 211, 915–916. <https://doi.org/10.1038/211915a0>
- Hansen, C., van der Meeren, G.I., Loeng, H., Skogen, M.D., 2021. Assessing the state of the Barents Sea using indicators: how, when, and where? *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 78, 2983–2998. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsab053>
- Hjøllo, S., Hansen, C., Skogen, M., 2021. Assessing the importance of zooplankton sampling patterns with an ecosystem model. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 680, 163–176. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps13774>
- Hjøllo, S.S., Huse, G., Skogen, M.D., Melle, W., 2012. Modelling secondary production in the Norwegian Sea with a fully coupled physical/primary production/individual-based *Calanus finmarchicus* model system. *Marine Biology Research* 8, 508–526. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17451000.2011.642805>
- Huse, G., Holst, J.C., Utne, K., Nøttestad, L., Melle, W., Slotte, A., Ottersen, G., Fenchel, T., Uiblein, F., 2012. Effects of interactions between fish populations on ecosystem dynamics in the Norwegian Sea – results of the INFERNO project. *Marine Biology Research* 8, 415–419. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17451000.2011.653372>
- Huse, G., Melle, W., Skogen, M.D., Hjøllo, S.S., Svendsen, E., Budgell, W.P., 2018. Modeling emergent life histories of copepods. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* 6, 23. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2018.00023>
- ICES, 2020. Working Group on the Integrated Assessments of the Norwegian Sea (WGINOR, 2019 meeting). *ICES Scientific Reports* 2, 52pp. <https://doi.org/10.17895/ices.pub.5996>
- Scheffer, M., Bavoco, J., de Angelis, D., Rose, K., van Nes, E., 1995. Super individuals a simple solution for modelling large populations on an individual basis. *Ecological Modelling* 80, 161–170. doi:10.1016/0304-3800(94)00055-M.
- Skaret, G., Dalpadado, P., Hjøllo, S.S., Skogen, M.D., Strand, E., 2014. *Calanus finmarchicus* abundance, production and population dynamics in the Barents Sea in a future climate. *Progress in Oceanography* 125, 26–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pocean.2014.04.008>
- Skjoldal, H.R., 2004. The Norwegian Sea ecosystem. Tapir academic press, Trondheim.
- Skogen, M.D., Ji, R., Akimova, A., Daewel, U., Hansen, C., Hjøllo, S., van Leeuwen, S., Maar, M., Macias, D., Mousing, E., Almroth-Rosell, E., Sailley, S., Spence, M., Troost, T., van de Wolfshaar, K., 2021. Disclosing the truth: Are models better than observations? *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps13574>
- Skogen, M.D., Olsen, A., Børsheim, K.Y., Sandø, A.B., Skjelvan, I., 2014. Modelling ocean acidification in the Nordic and Barents Seas in present and future climate. *Journal of Marine Systems* 131, 10–20. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2013.10.005>
- Skogen, M.D., Sjøiland, H., 1998. A user's guide to NORWECOM v2.0. The NORwegian ECOlogical Model system. (Technical Report No. 18/98), Fisker og Havet. Institute of Marine Research, Norway.
- Skogen, M.D., Svendsen, E., Berntsen, J., Aksnes, D., Ulvestad, K.B., 1995. Modelling the primary production in the North Sea using a coupled three-dimensional physical-chemical-biological

Model evaluation reporting form, OPE (Objective Patterns Evaluation)

ocean model. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 41, 545–565.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/0272-7714\(95\)90026-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0272-7714(95)90026-8)

Utne, K.R., Hjøllø, S.S., Huse, G., Skogen, M., 2012. Estimating the consumption of *Calanus finmarchicus* by planktivorous fish in the Norwegian Sea using a fully coupled 3D model system. *Marine Biology Research* 8, 527–547.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17451000.2011.642804>

Young, K.V., Dower, J.F., Pepin, P., 2009. A hierarchical analysis of the spatial distribution of larval fish prey. *Journal of Plankton Research* 31, 687–700. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbp017>